

Water-Energy Nexus: A Review of Technological Innovations for Resource Efficiency in Urban Water Systems in Malawi

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Suggested Citation

Zgambo, C.P., & Munthali, R.M. (2025). Water-Energy Nexus: A Review of Technological Innovations for Resource Efficiency in Urban Water Systems in Malawi. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(1), 227-242.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(1\).22](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(1).22)

Abstract:

The intricate and interdependent relationship between water and energy is crucial for sustainable development, especially in urban water systems. Malawi is facing challenges regarding water loss and energy use. Technological innovations such as Smart Water Systems and integrating renewable energy in the water-energy nexus must be deployed to enhance resource efficiency and address the pressing challenges of climate change, water scarcity, and energy shortages. Effective management of this relationship is critical for improving resource efficiency and ensuring the sustainability of urban water systems in Malawi. Adopting these technologies presents numerous benefits, including enhanced water supply reliability, consumer

behavioral change, improved energy efficiency, and reduced operational costs. However, several policy and regulatory challenges must also be addressed. This article explores the Water-Energy Nexus in urban water systems in Malawi by reviewing the situation and challenges, emerging technologies in water management and opportunities in integrating energy sources, and existing opportunities.

Keywords: *Renewable energy, Smart water systems, Hybrid systems, Energy efficiency.*

Introduction

Worldwide, about 2.2 billion people do not have access to safe drinking water, 70% of the global population are expected to face severe water shortage crises by 2050, according to the estimated water shortage trend (Organization, 2019; Salehi, 2022). The global water demand is expected to rise by 55%, while currently, around 25% of large cities are experiencing some levels of water stress (Lund Schlamovitz & Becker,

2021). In Sub-Saharan Africa, around 400 million individuals lack access to enhanced drinking water sources, constituting approximately 32% of the region's population (GOM, 2024; Yaya et al., 2019).

Urban water systems face significant challenges related to water loss and energy use, which are intricately linked. High water loss rates not only waste a vital resource but also lead to substantial energy consumption for treatment and distribution. The average water loss in developed

cities is around 20-30%, while developing regions may experience losses exceeding 40% primarily due to leaks and inefficiencies in infrastructure (Ahmad et al., 2020; Lam, 2017). Urban water supply and waste water treatment systems involve processes that are energy intensive. Moving raw water over long distances from the sources with support of pumping systems, treating, distributing it and meeting end-uses for various purposes account for some of the largest uses of electrical energy in some urban areas (Wilkinson, 2007). Unfortunately, energy consumption for water services is projected to increase due to urbanization and population growth, with urban water infrastructure contributing significantly to global CO₂ emissions (Younos et al., 2016).

Malawi faces significant challenges regarding water loss and energy use, particularly in urban areas and rural settings which are exacerbated by inadequate infrastructure and environmental issues such as climate change, population growth. The statistics reveal a concerning level of unaccounted for water (UFW) and inadequate energy access, which are critical for sustainable development. In Zomba City, UFW ranged from 20% to 36% between 1999 and 2008, with an average of 13% during a 2009 study, where real losses accounted for 81% of UFW (Hoko & Chipwaila, 2017). The Capital City Lilongwe reported UFW at 37.5% in 2012, exceeding the recommended 23% for developing countries, with real losses being the primary driver in specific areas (Harawa et al., 2016).

Given its relatively small landmass, large (and growing) population and heavy dependence on fuel wood, Malawi is an increasingly energy-stressed country. The National Energy Policy estimates that 96% of total energy demand is met by biomass energy. Households consume 84% of the total primary energy. A staggering 99% of household energy is supplied by biomass. This, with increasing population growth, is exerting significant pressure on the country's forest resources, leading to forest degradation and deforestation at a rate of 2.6% per year. 87% of the population uses firewood and 8% charcoal to satisfy their thermal energy needs (GOM, 2024). Less than 7% of the 14 million people are

connected to the national grid (Unuigbo & Ehizojie, 2024).

This review is essential because it addresses a significant gap in the academic literature, where the intersection of renewable energy and water management in Malawi has received insufficient attention. While there is a growing recognition of technological innovations potential in other sectors, its application within the water-energy nexus context in Malawi remains underexplored. Previous research tends to focus on individual technological innovations without considering their integration within the nexus or addressing the challenges and opportunities in Malawi.

Overview of the Water-Energy Nexus

The Water-Energy Nexus refers to the woven relationship between water and energy resources. Water and energy are the key resources to sustain life and are fundamental to national, regional and global economies (Jia et al., 2021). Water and energy highlight how these two critical resources affect one another's availability, management, and sustainability. Understanding this nexus is crucial for addressing current concerns such as climate change, resource scarcity, and environmental degradation.

The interdependence of the world's two most vital resources, water and energy, is attracting increased attention from both the scientific community and the general public (Hamiche et al., 2016). Water is required for each stage of energy production, and energy is critical for the availability and treatment of water (Khatib, 2016). Water and energy are tightly bound to the point that each depends on the other in a way that accessing water will require the available energy (Hussey & Pittock, 2012). The relationship between water and energy is becoming increasingly important to our societies' economic prosperity in the face of expanding population and climate change. Several environmental, political, economic, social, regulatory, and technological aspects influence the water-energy nexus (Bauer, 2014). Efficient use of energy decreases pressure on water resources, and vice versa (Dai et al., 2017). Water and electricity are inextricably intertwined, and these ties exist in all three categories:

production, transit, and consumption. The nexus's effects are being felt all across the world, as drought, climate change, industrial reform, and increased demand for water and electricity exacerbate the relationship (Hamiche et al., 2016). This nexus is multidimensional in nature.

In their research Hamiche et al. (2016) classified the nexus as environmental, technological dimensions - the interdependence of water and electricity sectors, noting how different technologies impact water usage and carbon emissions. As traditional resources deplete due to environmental pressures, the choice of technology becomes crucial. Key questions arise about the trade-offs between energy efficiency and water intensity in both industries.

Economic dimension - The economic dimension of the water-energy nexus is evolving due to reforms in Algeria's water and electricity sectors, promoting competition and transitioning to cost recovery pricing. These changes affect market structures and pricing strategies, impacting resource valuation and consumption, with examples from India and Gabon highlighting broader social and environmental implications.

Social dimension - Water and electricity are essential for society, intertwining with social dynamics, especially for those directly affected, like irrigators facing drought-related trade-offs. Climate change exacerbates these links, influencing consumption and perceptions of value. Public attitudes toward conservation are shifting, but challenges remain in addressing sustainability and societal perceptions regarding resource management.

Lastly the Political dimensions - The political dimension significantly affects the water-energy nexus, with industry reforms creating markets that complicate interconnections. Stricter environmental regulations may necessitate energy-intensive processes, conflicting with carbon reduction goals. Isolated policy development in both sectors leads to inefficiencies; integrated, flexible policies are essential to address emerging challenges from climate change and resource demands.

Current situation and challenges in Malawi

Urban energy-water management in Malawi presents a unique set of challenges that arise due to the intricate relationship between water resources and energy supply. As urbanization accelerates, the demand for both water and energy rises, putting significant strain on existing systems and infrastructure.

Dependence on Hydropower

Hydroenergy is a type of renewable energy that can reduce reliance on fossil fuels while also influencing national food, water, and energy security. If water is abundant, it is a clean and renewable source for creating electricity, which can significantly improve macro-level energy security (Hellegers et al., 2008). The Electricity Supply Corporation of Malawi (ESCOM) generates almost all of Malawi's electricity by hydropower, making it vulnerable due to its reliance on Lake Malawi. Malawi's four power plants are stationed along its major river, the Shire, which is the only outflow from Lake Malawi, hence their capacity to function is greatly dependent on the lake's water levels (Nielsen et al., 2015). Recent droughts and sedimentation in the lake through erosion, mainly from increased land clearing for agriculture in the watershed areas, have caused low water levels, resulting in unstable energy production and frequent outages (UNDP, 2007).

Water Scarcity and Demand

Water shortage in urban areas of Malawi is a critical problem exacerbated by fast urbanization, climate change, and insufficient infrastructure. Many urban areas in Malawi suffer from aging and poorly maintained water supply systems, leading to frequent disruptions (Mpakati Gama & Mkandawire, 2015). More than 70% of the city's population resides in informal settlements, where access to water is significantly restricted, and elevated rates of nonfunctional community kiosks accompany this situation (Adams, 2018). Additionally, the regular load shedding that occurs throughout Malawi is one of the most significant difficulties in urban water and energy

management. The scheduled, routine power outage disturbs daily living and adversely impacts businesses that require energy to operate including water supply. Water supply is limited since water treatment and delivery use grid electricity. As a result, operating costs increase dramatically, affecting the broader economy and raising consumer prices (World Bank, 2020).

Climate Change Impact

Climate change exacerbates water scarcity, affecting both supply and quality, particularly in developing nations like Malawi (Talat, 2021). Extreme weather events, as well as forced migration, political instability, famine, declining labour productivity, poor sanitation, and deterioration in public health, pose significant threats to African transportation, telecommunications, and water supply infrastructure, as well as energy assets. Energy infrastructure is particularly vulnerable to many of the extreme weather events that are set to become more severe and frequent (Senyagwa, 2022). Climate change and human activities increase water problems by diminishing water availability and deteriorating water quality. The inadequate focus on ecological upkeep leads to pollution becoming increasingly prevalent in the public water distribution system around the world. Malawi, like many other Sub-Saharan countries, has a poor investment climate, making it difficult to expand energy sector production capacity. Given the magnitude of capital required in the energy sector, emerging countries have limited options and have therefore resorted to avenues that attract private investments, which also requires the government to reform the energy sector (Authority, 2019; Johnson et al., 2017).

Infrastructure Deficiencies

The water supply infrastructure in Malawi's urban areas is severely deficient, leading to considerable challenges with water accessibility. A significant number of systems are outdated, with a considerable segment of the pipeline infrastructure over 60 years in age, resulting in recurrent failures and inefficiency (Chipwaila, 2009). Moreover, non-revenue water (NRW) percentages in towns and cities might be very

elevated; for instance, Blantyre's water utility reports NRW rates ranging from 40% to 49%, signifying considerable losses before water reaching customers (Magombo & Kosamu, 2016). Modernized water delivery systems are urgently needed to solve existing water challenges by boosting water supply efficiency and addressing sustainable water management internationally (Choi GyeWoon et al., 2016).

Inadequate Access to Safe Drinking Water

Approximately 663 million people worldwide do not have access to safe drinking water, with over half living in Sub-Saharan Africa, including Malawi, where just 68% of the population has improved drinking water sources (Phiri, 2017). Domestic poor water availability, quality, and sanitation services are still an issue in developing countries, and public utilities provide approximately 90% of sanitation and water delivery to urban areas (Kalulu & Hoko, 2010). Water pollution is another big difficulty that most developing countries face, with poor sanitation systems (Manda et al., 2016). Malawi's poor solid waste management is causing water quality problems. Unauthorized dumping activities cause contamination of water supplies, posing health dangers to populations (Wisdom & Sithik, 2024). The bulk of rural homes rely on boreholes, which frequently exhibit difficulties such as low yield and frequent non-operationality (Phiri, 2017).

Governance and Regulatory Challenges

In pursuit of achieving universal access to energy, the United Nations came up with the ambitious Sustainable Development Goal Seven (SDG 7), which intends to secure access to affordable, dependable, sustainable, and modern energy for all by 2030 (IRENA, 2024). Currently, the world relies on energy for practically everything, thus improving access to modern energy will be critical in moving developing countries like Malawi to sustained economic growth (Banerjee et al., 2015; Borgstein et al., 2019). Progress toward increased access to modern energy requires long-term determinations to develop the legislative and regulatory environment, in addition to having strong institutions that can enforce national

legislation (Urpelainen, 2018). However, the existing legal, institutional framework and institutional procedures continue to provide a substantial hurdle to the growth of the energy sector in developing nations, including Malawi, particularly in terms of renewable energy (Chamdimba et al., 2021). For example in Blantyre, governance issues have been identified as primary factors contributing to water shortages, supported by inadequate tariff structures that fail to promote efficient water management practices (Magombo & Kosamu, 2016).

Emerging Technologies in Water Management

Emerging technologies in water management are revolutionizing how water resources are monitored, managed, and used. These technologies are critical for enhancing efficiency, sustainability, and resilience in water systems. Energy conservation (EC) refers to utilizing less energy through behavioural modifications. In contrast, energy efficiency (EE) refers to the efficient use of energy through the use of technology that consumes less power (Banerjee et al., 2015). Emerging technologies are playing a critical role in transforming water management practices, addressing various challenges such as resource scarcity, contamination, and inefficient distribution systems. This paper discusses two kinds of integrations that can yield resource efficiency and sustainability

Smart Water Systems

Due to the rising difficulties of water-related problems such as water scarcity, water degradation, and aging infrastructure, conventional methodologies, and management for drinking water supply have steadily displayed their limitations and incapability to solve these water issues (Nguyen et al., 2018). Traditionally, engineers and researchers became accustomed to resizing water-supply systems.

However, updating the present water distribution network is time-consuming and costly. Instead, consider modernizing the water system with smart components including

sensors, controls, and a data centre (Sonaje & Joshi, 2015). Water utilities may now remotely adjust crucial parameters both upstream and downstream of the water treatment stage utilizing improved sensing techniques developed in recent decades (Kennedy et al., 2009).

The deployment of smart water systems has numerous substantial advantages influencing both water and energy efficiency. Smart water systems attempt to implement the Internet of Things (IoT) technology across the water supply infrastructure and consumers' consumption. The integration of IoT-enabled devices enables real-time monitoring of water levels, flow rates, and quality, which may lead to informed decision-making on resource management. Additionally, these systems can discover leaks and inefficiencies rapidly, allowing fast repairs that save water and minimize energy usage related to water treatment and distribution (Gowthaman & Arulmozhi, 2023; Koo et al., 2015).

Smart water system illustrates many of the ways technology, middleware, and software help maximize the value of Smart Metering data to all stakeholders general for natural resource managers. Smart meter technologies provide access to real-time data related to water and associated energy consumption. They also provide opportunities for efficiency improvements, namely efficient water uses in the household and utility-level control of water losses and cost-benefit water planning (Loureiro et al., 2014).

Li et al. (2020) classified the Smart Water System into five levels (from bottom to top) instruments layer, function layer, property layer, benefits layer, and application layer, that are suggested to comprehend how systematic architecture is applied in the SWS framework. The instrumentation layer of a Smart Water System (SWS) incorporates both physical infrastructure and cyberinfrastructure. Physical components, such as pipes, valves, and pumps, comprise the basic framework of the water system but do not allow smart functions on their own. In contrast, cyberinfrastructure contains modern equipment like smart sensors, pumps, and valves, which

boost the system's capabilities. Unlike typical water distribution systems that simply provide basic flow or pressure data, SWS leverages cyber instruments to offer extensive diagnostic information, allowing fast leak detection and automatic solutions.

The relationship between physical and cyber aspects is critical; the physical infrastructure creates essential data, which cyber technologies gather, process, and evaluate. This synergy enables for enhanced operation and maintenance of the physical components based on real-time data insights. For example, automated meters provide bi-directional communication, enabling them to regulate equipment like as valves. Different smart sensors are also customized to solve unique issues inside the system. Ultimately, the instrumentation layer of SWS must successfully integrate both physical and cyber components to improve water management and boost system intelligence.

Smart Water Metering

One of the components of the smart water system is smart water metering. The conventional approach to the issue of shortage is to utilize a range of strategies to save water, which means using less water while avoiding or eliminating waste. Besides that water conservation in urban areas has increasingly taken an integrated management approach, and has gone beyond the use of measures such as flow-restricting taps and showers, optimization of toilet and urinal flushing, and now commonly includes the use of water-efficient appliances and technologies like waterless urinals, electronic taps, automatic leak detection, rainwater harvesting and effluent water reuse (Hauber-Davidson & Idris, 2006), possibly the most successful approach that is frequently employed for good urban water management is water metering. (Beal & Flynn, 2014) describes water metering as the integration of meter data into a business system (e.g. Billing system) and the sharing of information with consumers. A smart water meter configuration involves a high-resolution water meter linked to a data logger, which captures water use data that can be downloaded as an electronic signal and analysed

using available technology (Beal et al., 2016; Britton et al., 2008).

The aim of a water meter is to monitor the quantity of water (typically on a volumetric basis such as liters or mega litres) given to a customer over a set time, mainly for billing reasons (Nguyen et al., 2018). Most cities charge residential customers with a basic fixed wastewater fee or a straightforward volumetric wastewater charge depending on their water use. Autoflow© delivers end usage data for each home, which enables water service providers to evaluate more complex wastewater rates that better represent the real cost of treating a specific household's wastewater. Such cost-reflective rates might be based on the amount of water entering the sewerage system (i.e. omit agricultural end use) and the characteristics of effluent from each dwelling. The characteristics of an individual household's wastewater might be approximated using the water end-use data collected from Autoflow© and the usual chemical contents of those end-use categories (e.g. wastewater from a dishwasher needs more treatment than bath wastewater)

SWM technology enables water authorities to collect water meter readings remotely and at a greater frequency, and in a format that can be employed for many objectives like demand and consumption control, leakage identification and water saving (Drubin, 2016). Smart water meters have proved successful in avoiding leaks, a rising problem. Water is a cheaper commodity than gas in many countries, but breaches in household and distribution networks may be difficult to detect. The growing emphasis on sustainability has contributed to the expansion of the smart water metering industry, which attempts to prevent water leaks (Loureiro et al., 2014).

Understanding how customers consumed water is crucial for planning and implementing wastewater treatment technology. Autoflow© monitors residential customers' end-use demand (e.g. shower, tap, clothes washer) throughout the day. Knowing the quantity of outdoor consumption consumed largely for irrigation is significant in calculating the amount of effluent entering the sewage system from each house.

Detailed information on wastewater produced from a given site can equip infrastructure planners with strong data when building and planning for future surrounding growth zones. The planner would have a more specific assessment of the present sewage system's real capacity, which would enable them to determine whether to update the system or utilize the existing sewerage pipe network. Finally, knowing the volume of water and typical chemical contents of each end use category (for example, clothes washing wastewater quality) at various times of the day may be utilized for more proactive wastewater treatment plant operations management (Nguyen et al., 2018).

Integration of Renewable Energy Sources

Hybrid systems

The integration of hybrid and smart water systems into Malawi's water delivery infrastructure is vital for enhancing water access, efficiency, and sustainability. Given the country's limitations, such as climatic unpredictability, insufficient infrastructure, and limited resources, merging hybrid renewable energy systems with cutting-edge smart technology has the potential to transform water management approaches.

A hybrid power system integrates more than one energy source. Energy systems that depend on a single resource have the downside of growing large when the resource is limited. Hybrid systems depend on numerous resources, making them more reliable even when one is unavailable. Combining wind energy with solar energy in hybrid systems boosts the reliability and efficiency of water delivery operations. In such installations, both wind turbines and solar panels work together to offer a constant energy source for water pumping and treatment systems. During periods of low wind, solar energy can compensate, ensuring an uninterrupted water supply (Energy, 2016). This synergy not only improves energy management but also provides for enhanced flexibility in operation, reacting to shifting climatic circumstances.

Recent breakthroughs in tiny generating technologies, plus greater efficiency and decreased prices, are boosting the development of decentralized energy systems, even in locations with established power networks. This tendency is projected to remain despite increased urbanization, population expansion, and economic development. Consequently, the global energy landscape will likely stay hybrid, including both centralized and decentralized generation. Centralized systems will be important for big cities, but decentralized alternatives may cover the energy demands of millions in rural and peri-urban regions. Therefore, it's necessary to build hybrid policies, regulatory frameworks, and economic models within a comprehensive national energy and water plan, especially with renewable energy integration (Jones & Olsson, 2017).

Smart water systems are progressively embracing renewable energy sources, such as solar electricity or wind energy, to promote sustainability. By eliminating dependence on fossil fuels, these systems not only cut operating costs but also limit their environmental imprint and offer a robust water supply, particularly in places prone to climate change. Renewable energy sources such as wind, geothermal heat, solar power, biofuel, and hydropower have gained substantial attention in various policy papers and empirical research studies owing to their vital role in reducing energy difficulties and environmental deterioration (Sharif et al., 2020; Shoukat et al., 2021; Ullah & Sharif, 2022)

Solar Energy

Solar energy is a fast-developing type of renewable energy that is undergoing tremendous worldwide growth (Raihan, 2023). Solar panels can be deployed to power water pumping stations, treatment facilities, and sensors within the water distribution network. Solar energy systems, particularly photovoltaic (PV) arrays, are advantageous in locations with ample sunlight, significantly lowering electricity costs and reducing carbon emissions (Mojtahed et al., 2023). Solar-powered water pumps have various benefits over traditional pumping systems (Aliyu et al., 2018). Solar energy is the most sustainable

source since it is clean and plentiful, needs minimum maintenance, does not cause noise, easy to install and use solar PV panels transfer sunlight directly into useable electrical energy, which is, in return, used to power the water pump directly or via an inverter(Obaideen et al., 2023). The development in PV water pumping systems leads to economy development in rural areas (Periasamy et al., 2015).

Additionally, photovoltaic water pumping plays a crucial role in supplying potable water; especially to some areas where electricity supply from the national grid is very limited(Aliyu et al., 2018). Also using solar resources to substitute fossil fuel (diesel) in powering water pumps would lessen the emissions of greenhouse gas which may emerge from the usage of fossil fuels. (Ramos & Ramos, 2009) reported a reduction of 1030 Mg in CO₂ emission when a hybrid solar, wind, and hydro-water pumping system was used. The employment of solar resources in water pumping systems would enhance agricultural or grassland production consequently, increasing the carbon sink (Aliyu et al., 2018).

Wind Energy

Wind energy systems extract kinetic energy from the wind via the use of turbines. Wind farms may be erected on land or offshore, with offshore wind farms frequently generating greater energy outputs owing to stronger and more constant winds. The components of wind energy systems comprise rotor blades, a generator, and a control system that maximizes energy output. Wind energy has undergone tremendous cost reductions and technical breakthroughs, contributing to its fast rise as a key source of renewable energy throughout the world. Wind and solar PV made up 90% of the global investments in electric power in 2015(Medinilla & Sergejeff, 2023) and are now competitive with conventional electric power generation since the cost of wind turbines has fallen by some 40% since 2009 while the price of solar PV has been reduced by 80%(Jones & Olsson, 2017). Wind turbines can provide energy to power water systems, particularly in areas with substantial wind resources. The generated energy can be

used to operate pumps and water treatment systems, contributing to improved energy efficiency and reliability(Mojtahed et al., 2023).

Opportunities of Integrating Technological Innovations in Urban Water Systems

Malawi is a landlocked nation in southeast Africa, surrounded by Zambia, Tanzania, and Mozambique. It is marked by its distinctive terrain, which includes the Great Rift Valley and stretches along the gorgeous beaches of Lake Malawi, one of Africa's biggest lakes. The country's population is predicted to reach above 19 million people, with a high population density impacting a range of socioeconomic variables, including resource management(Back et al., 2018; Palamuleni, 2023). Approximately 65% of the population has access to improved water sources, but this figure is unevenly distributed, particularly between urban and rural areas(Lubanga et al., 2023).

Figure 1. The Location of Malawi on the African Map

Source: Asia & Lanka, 2017

Malawi predominantly relies on biomass, such as firewood and charcoal, for energy, accounting for roughly 90% of total energy use. This dependence on biomass not only leads to deforestation but also adds to severe indoor air pollution, which causes health problems, particularly for women and children(Nyanhanda et al., 2023). The country has limited access to

electricity, with only about 15% of the population connected to the grid(Sachathap et al., 2021). Rural electrification remains a particular challenge, hindering economic development and access to modern services.

Water and energy issues in Malawi are closely interconnected. The majority of electricity generation is hydropower-based, generated from the Shire River, which is fed by Lake Malawi. However, seasonal variations in rainfall affect water levels and consequently the capacity to generate hydroelectric power(Harrington et al., 2024). This vulnerability underlines the need of tackling both water management and energy generation to develop a more resilient system that can survive climatic unpredictability. Sustainable management approaches such as smart water metering and hybrid systems in water distribution systems may produce several advantages for Malawi. These technologies may promote resource efficiency, improve service delivery, and enable sustainable management of water resources.

Smart water metering permits thorough surveillance of water usage patterns, enabling for improved diagnosis of leaks and promoting conservation practices among users. With real-time data, utilities can react rapidly to anomalous demand spikes, signalling possible leaks or waste. Thames Water, the largest water and wastewater services company in the UK, implemented advanced smart metering technologies (Fosso Wamba et al., 2018). Through these systems, they significantly reduced water losses by approximately 25% over a specified period. In the year 2005 alone, the project was anticipated to have saved 23 million litres a day – enough to supply more than 130,000 people(Mergelas et al., 2006). This system also helped Thames to proactively inform consumers about their water usage. This initiative led to improved customer satisfaction and reduced operational costs associated with leak detection and repair(Fosso Wamba et al., 2018).

Smart contracts enable effective water distribution through the use of real-time demand and quality data, therefore minimizing waste and

enhancing resource allocation(Samanta & Sarkar, 2023). Sydney Water used advanced metering infrastructure (AMI) to monitor water consumption in real time. The technology proved important in reacting to drought situations, allowing the utility to execute targeted water conservation measures. Customers could monitor their consumption patterns and modify their use appropriately, resulting in considerable water savings of between 7% and 10% (Doolan, 2011).

Smart water meters enable consumers to monitor their water usage closely, fostering awareness and accountability (Rajalakshmi et al., 2024). Liu et al. (2015) had a study intended to establish if individualized water-use feedback via smart metering may drive behavioural changes toward more sustainable water usage. According to the data, 38% of families have adjusted their water-use behaviours, such as taking shorter showers and saving tap water. Some households installed water-saving equipment or fixed leaks. Finally, the intervention group dropped their average water consumption by 20.3% following intervention, compared to a 12.7% decline in the control group. This resulted in an 8% net effect of water savings for the intervention group.

Implementing micro-turbines in water distribution systems can convert excess hydraulic energy into electricity, contributing to energy efficiency and leakage control (Giudicianni et al., 2020). At the Athens Plant Nursery in Greece, renewable energy and innovative wastewater management technologies were integrated into the wastewater system, and the results showed a significant 32% reduction in average power consumption through operational adjustments. Simulations indicated that incorporating solar PV could significantly lower electricity costs, with trade-offs identified between the area occupied by PV panels and overall expenses. Both high-efficiency and conventional pan(Zisos et al., 2024).

Jordan, like Malawi, faces issues such as water constraint, energy dependency, and climate change. A project to integrate renewable energy into the water treatment system is now progress.

The feasibility analysis demonstrated that using renewable energy for desalination can drastically reduce the cost of water production. According to studies, solar energy can lower prices by up to 50%, making desalinated water more affordable for agricultural and home use.

Additionally, by reducing dependency on fossil fuels, Jordan can improve its energy security, assuring a steady and consistent energy source for desalination processes (Albatayneh, 2024). Adopting hybrid systems in water systems leads to large savings of installed electric power capacity and of diesel and will reduce huge amounts of CO₂ emissions, hence increasing access to improved water.

Policy and Regulatory Framework

The urban water system in Malawi works under a comprehensive policy framework intended to control and guarantee the sustainable use of water resources. This framework covers numerous laws, rules, and institutional structures developed to address the expanding needs for water supply and sanitation in metropolitan areas.

The 2019 National Urban Policy is an important document that offers solutions to handle urban growth concerns, including water management. This policy aims to foster sustainable urbanization through integrated planning and resource management, recognizing the vital role of water in urban environments (GOM, 2024). Another key document is the National Water Policy, which gives general recommendations on water resource management, laying the foundation for more comprehensive.

The Water Resources Act of 2013 serves as the cornerstone of the legislative framework for managing water resources in Malawi (GOM, 2024). It is meant to provide for the management, conservation, use, and control of water resources, and it established the Water Resources Board to supervise enforcement and compliance. Furthermore, the Water Resources Regulations of 2018 augment this legislation by specifying specific criteria, including water usage licenses and conservation measures to safeguard water quality and availability.

Despite the established structure, Malawi's urban water system confronts various obstacles, including governance concerns, enforcement of laws, and insufficient public knowledge (Chunga et al., 2022). Additionally, delays in implementing legislation and the consequences of climate change worsen water shortages and management challenges, compromising service delivery and sustainability (Chiluwe & Nkhata, 2014; Chunga et al., 2022).

Future Research Directions

The research on technological innovations and Resource Efficiency in urban water distribution systems in Malawi provides a basic understanding, but some gaps require further investigation for improved waste management strategies and policy frameworks.

Economic Analysis of Integrating the Hybrid Systems in Water Treatment Systems in Malawi

Analysing the potential cost savings associated with reduced energy consumption and operational costs when using hybrid systems compared to conventional energy sources, and how this can improve water quality and accessibility for communities, thereby addressing public health challenges associated with water scarcity and contamination.

Behavioural Studies on Water Management Practices in Malawi

Identifying and analysing individual and community water usage and management trends, as well as attitudes and views about water shortages, conservation initiatives, and the success of present water management regulations.

Conclusion

Summary of Key Findings:

In conclusion, the interaction of water and energy resources poses both enormous obstacles and important potential for Malawi's urban water systems. The high percentages of

unaccounted-for water and energy inefficiencies underline the need for new solutions. Emerging technologies, such as smart water metering and hybrid renewable energy systems, provide prospective avenues to boost resource efficiency, improve service delivery, and encourage sustainable management practices. Moreover, addressing the policy and legislative challenges and environmental dynamics within the water-energy nexus is vital for overcoming the hurdles to successful resource management. Future research should concentrate on establishing frameworks that incorporate these technologies while addressing local settings and stakeholder interaction. Collaborative efforts among government, private sector, and communities are important for implementing these innovations effectively, guaranteeing that Malawi can accomplish its sustainable development objectives while providing access to clean water and dependable electricity for everyone.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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